

FASHION aLIVE

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PROJECT ACRONYM	Fashion Alive
DURATION	24 months
WEBSITE	https://fashion-alive.com/
PROJECT COORDINATOR	Gisela Fortuna - CREAMODITE
COORDINATOR CONTACT	gisela@workef.com

WORK PACKAGE	6
WORK PACKAGE LEADER	CREAMODITE
RESPONSIBLE	Creamodite (lead beneficiary)
DELIVERABLE VERSION NUMBER	0.3
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU - Public

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ABSTRACT	The following document compiles information on milestone 5, regarding the publication of the Fashion Alive website and social media.
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TABLE OF MODIFICATIONS

Version	Date	Author	Reason for change
v.0.1	10/11/2022	Yilmaz Vurucu, XsentrikArts	
v.02	19/11/2022	Creamodite	Comments and suggestions
V.03	26/11/2022	Yilmaz Vurucu, XsentrikArts	Final version

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1. About Fashion Alive

Developing a sustainable and positive fashion landscape is becoming imperative on a global scale, but the path towards sustainable fashion remains ambiguous and hard to achieve in most cases. Addressing this issue needs international collaboration. The FASHION ALIVE Project main approach is the promotion of sustainable practices in the creative fashion industry by generating attractive events to engage wider audiences and raise their awareness on this important subject. FASHION ALIVE Project approach is therefore underpinned by the following concepts:

CREAMODITE (Spain), UMINHO (Portugal) and UCAMPANIA (Italy) will conceptualise and experiment with the creation of sustainable fashion methods, where each partner will work on a specific innovative methodology. CREAMODITE (Spain) will hold a zero-waste design and pattern making contest, with the winning designs obtaining the opportunity to exhibit their work and take part in the Fashion Alive Event in Madrid.

In parallel, XSENTRIK (Austria) will explore and envisage a digital and audio-visual strategy using technological tools (combining videos, 3-D projections, video mapping software, sounds, lights and music) that will be adapted to a living fashion show.

The creations of the four partners will be displayed to the public during 3 non-conventional fashion and arts events that will combine the exhibition/catwalk of the sustainable creations by CREAMODITE, UMINHO and UCAMPANIA with the digital and audio-visual creations by XSENTRIKARTS.

The events will take place during 2 different days, as there will be another more participative session with roundtables, talks, conferences and public discussions about arts, sustainability, fashion and creativity. After the presentation of the sustainable fashion solutions at the project events, the partners will perform an analysis to evaluate the impact gathered through the innovative events to understand how the message of sustainable fashion arrives to general public through this kind of engaging and cultural expressions.

2. Project Website

a. Website design

The project website design was based on the visual identity created for the project, incorporating the logos, fonts and visual elements detailed in D6.1 – Communications and Dissemination Plan.

b. Website purposes

The project website (www.fashion-alive.com) will serve the following functions:

- A) Provide an overview of the project, its goals and aims, and sustainable fashion. It will serve as a portal that provides information about the project, the partners, and the concept.
- A) Function as a source of news: latest developments on the project will be disseminated via the website and the blog entry posts. In this regard, the “news” section will be the most dynamic and regularly updated segment of the site.
- B) The editorials published will allow for in-depth examination on the subjects and themes surrounding sustainable and zero waste fashion. In this regard, it will also serve as a tool that disseminates concepts and promotes zero waste and circular fashion. The editorials will appeal more to industry professionals, researchers, designers and students of fashion design.
- C) The site will provide information about the project implementation to various external audiences. In doing so, it will become a process diary documenting the project and facilitating its analysis.
- D) Thus, the webpage will serve as one of the main dissemination channels, with all the news, editorials, and developments initially being entered as blog entries prior to distribution via the Fashion Alive social media channels.

c. Website content

The website is structured into the following pages:

- i. Home page: contains a summary of the Fashion Alive project’s mission and goals, gathers the latest blog entries, and includes an introduction to the project partners.

www.fashion-alive.com

THE FUTURE OF SUSTAINABLE FASHION

FUNDED BY THE EU

Hero section, expressing the project's mission.

Fashion Alive is an international collaboration. We're a platform dedicated to the development and promotion of zero waste pattern-making and fashion design. Through the utilization of unique methods and approaches in the creation of designs, we will ignite exchange, inspiration and the transfer of know-how across borders and boundaries.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Summary of the project's mission and objectives. Contains a link to the "About Us" page.

LATEST NEWS

Here's what's been going on

FASHION ALIVE LAB AT UNICAMPANIA
November 28, 2022

Taking place on November 18, 2022 and organized by Fashion Alive partners UNICAMPANIA, the workshop focused on analyzing the progress of the FASHION ALIVE project within

[READ MORE »](#)

WHY DOES SUSTAINABLE FASHION MATTER?
November 21, 2022

Since the industrial revolution, the textile and the fashion industry have taken an accelerated path. Every year around 80 billion garments are produced worldwide, 400% more than

[READ MORE »](#)

Latest news section, gathering the latest blog entries about the project developments.

PARTNERS

CREAMODITE

is a Spanish association of ateliers of arts and design, whose main mission is to dynamize and recover the value of local creative industries, with a special focus on fashion.

[LEARN MORE](#)

UMINHO

The Department of Textile Engineering at the School of Engineering in Guimaraes (Portugal) has been developing research activities in the area of Fibrous Material Engineering and Design for a few decades.

[LEARN MORE](#)

UNICAMPANIA

The Department of Architecture and Industrial Design of the University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" carries out, promotes and supports research, basic and applied, in the fields of architecture, industrial design, cultural heritage, urban context, of the government of the territory and of the landscape.

[LEARN MORE](#)

XSENTRIK ARTS

...is an Austrian interdisciplinary arts platform with a focus on utilizing the power of storytelling to inspire and create change; promote diversity and equality; advocate sustainable, healthy living solutions and dialogue in lives and spaces.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Partners section, provides a brief introduction of the partner's organisation and their role in the Fashion Alive project

- ii. News: Contains the archive of blog entries created about project updates and events. The entries are categorized according to the sustainable fashion research area and partner.

<https://fashion-alive.com/latest-news>

Blog page title and categories menu

Blog post archive. To date, 5 posts have been created.

<https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-lab-at-unicampania>

<https://fashion-alive.com/why-does-sustainable-fashion-matter>

<https://fashion-alive.com/applying-the-zero-waste-concept-to-leather>

<https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-launches-contests-2>

<https://fashion-alive.com/we-meet-in-madrid-2>

- iii. Blog post formats: Two blog post templates have been created.
 - a. A more dynamic image-based layout designed to post behind-the-scenes content about the development of fashion collections, videomapping animation, and partner meetings.
- <https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-lab-at-unicampania>

ANALYZING TRADITIONAL TEXTILE MANUFACTURING METHODS

Dealing with sustainable fashion research by experimenting with the cultural heritage and analyzing the typical handicraft textile manufacturing of the Campania region, the workshop also focused on the heritage framework of ancient textile techniques.

Various innovative approaches were tried out, using new and traditional technologies, with which to give continuity to the trousseau tradition.

Moving around a transdisciplinary vision that connects different knowledge – such as fashion and contemporary art, textile manipulation, advanced production processes – the workshop investigated an experimental circular fashion system through the hybridization of particular craft techniques.

PHOTOS FROM THE WORKSHOP

- iv. A text-based template, designed to share essay-style content on sustainable fashion concepts and ideas.

<https://fashion-alive.com/why-does-sustainable-fashion-matter>

FASHION ALIVE Home News About Contact Partners

WHY SUSTAINABLE FASHION MATTERS

CREAMODITE

21.11.2022

Since the industrial revolution, the textile and the fashion industry have taken an accelerated path. Every year around 80 billion garments are produced worldwide, 400% more than what we used to produce 20 years ago. The up-scaling of fashion for the mass market has brought cheap prices and accessibility for a wider audience. But at what cost?

WHY DOES SUSTAINABLE FASHION MATTER?

Since the industrial revolution, the textile and the fashion industry have taken an accelerated path. Every year around 80 billion garments are produced worldwide, 400% more than what we used to produce 20 years ago.

The up-scaling of fashion for the mass market has brought cheap prices and accessibility for a wider audience. But at what cost?

"THERE IS NO BEAUTY IN THE FINEST CLOTH IF IT CREATES HUNGER AND UNHAPPINESS" MAHATMA GANDHI

PROBLEMS OF A LINEAR ECONOMY

The linear economy model that has been ruling industries for at least 20 years, has enabled a pattern of over-consumption at low prices. But what are the real repercussions behind this accelerated industry?

In the last decade, the main goal of enterprises has been financial growth, without measuring the real impacts caused by this growth.

We must consider that low-cost garments are possible due to a cost reduction in their manufacturing process. This means there is always someone paying the real cost of clothes with unethical practices, poor quality, and other cost-lowering actions taken on to ensure such cheap prices could be offered to the consumer.

The fast fashion model creates around 52 low-cost collections instead of the usual 2 to 4 that the fashion industry normally does. This creates huge social and environmental consequences.

There are many issues along the chain of value, one of them is the manufacturing process where unethical and unfair practices take place exploiting human and natural resources to offer cheap and fast products for an accelerated demand.

Here's a list of some of the activities that permit a low-cost system:

- Low quality and non-durable materials
- Cheap Labor, which in many cases involve unethical and unsafe practices, low life quality for the workers and child labor.
- Use of toxic substances during the finishing process of fabrics and garments, as well as chemical waste that pollutes water.
- Bad practices during the care and post-consumption of the garments.
- other similar practices

JOIN THE CHANGE!

Trends and today's culture promotes the over-consumption.

We can find data that estimates a garment is used 7 times before being discarded, a clear example of this is the 35 kg of textile waste that are created per person every year worldwide.

NOWADAYS WE ARE FACING A CRITICAL GLOBAL SITUATION THAT INVITES US TO ACT FAST AND JOIN THE CHANGE.

We need to understand that everything is connected, so we can act from our role as a consumer, entrepreneur, business, manufacturer, or government to implement the needed measures to transform and be a more responsible version of ourselves.

If we are part of the problem, we have the enormous opportunity to be part of the solution.

LET'S START NOW!

The responsibility to be more sustainable has a potential from a consumer perspective: better habits and supporting the right changes pushes the industry to change as well, with every purchase.

NONETHELESS, DESIGNERS HAVE ALSO A HUGE RESPONSIBILITY TO LOOK FOR NEW ALTERNATIVES FOR BETTER AND A MORE RESPONSIBLE DESIGN THAT PERMITS US TO MITIGATE TODAY'S IMPACTS.

If you are a designer with an interest in promoting a responsible and sustainable fashion industry, we want to invite you to send us your proposals and participate in our sustainable fashion contest!

More info on how you can take part, [here in Spanish](#), and [here in English!](#)

Original article written by [Ximena Corcuero](#) for Creamedite Access original article in Spanish [here](#).

SPREAD THE WORD

- v. About Fashion Alive: This page gathers all the relevant information about the project's mission, goals and the steps that will be carried out to achieve the proposed results in developing and disseminating sustainable fashion methods and concepts.

<https://fashion-alive.com/about-us>

ABOUT US

MORE ON FASHION ALIVE

As 'fast fashion' becomes more accessible and available, the repercussions of such a production and consumption model are tremendous, with significant impact on our planet, environment, society and future. As Fashion Alive, we've come to recognize the pressing need to move away from fast fashion.

Developing a sustainable and positive fashion landscape is becoming imperative on a global scale, but the path towards sustainable fashion remains ambiguous and hard to achieve in most cases.

COLLABORATIVE IMPACT

Addressing this issue needs international collaboration: it is only through joint efforts and local impact that we can raise awareness and transfer knowledge and methodologies.

Collaboration at a European level is required to combine different sources of expertise and present solutions in a unified and diverse way, with direct impact on each of the participating countries, as well as indirectly on the rest of Europe.

We will be providing access to project developments and results thanks to our online dissemination activities and will be relaying our experiences each step of the way.

SPEAKING OF STEPS...

HERE'S A BRIEF ROADMAP OF WHAT WE'VE SET OUT TO ACCOMPLISH.

1. ZERO WASTE

Our lead partner CREAMODITE will develop experimental methods to reach the so called Zero Waste Fashion concept. This goal will be achieved by generating knowledge on new systems to design clothes producing zero or little waste when manipulating the materials and garments.

Considering that roughly 15 percent of the fabric is discarded when a typical garment is made, the cumulative effect of leaving behind no waste has far-reaching environmental consequences. Zero Waste is also about working within those constraints to invent beautiful new forms of fashion.

FOLLOW OUR PROGRESS

2. CIRCULAR FASHION

UMINHO will centre their creations around sustainable materials and the concept of Circular Fashion. Experimenting with new business models that allow for the reuse of discarded fabrics by the textile and apparel industry will create a precedent for such a model.

This approach will also entail the development of means to extend the life of stopped fabrics, stockpiles, clothes cuts leftovers or small rolls of fabric and scraps; enabling them to circulate again and extending their life cycles.

In order to use preexisting clothing, accessories or other items and restructure them into new garments, a collection and awareness campaign will be launched: increasing the the conscientious disposal of end-of-life clothing. A collection of 15-20 experimental pieces and prototypes that use recycled fabrics, which will be later exhibited in the second stage of the project.

FOLLOW OUR PROGRESS

3. CULTURAL HERITAGE

UMCAMPANA will provide input through their research on experimental sustainable fashion from a cultural heritage perspective. This process will involve the analysis of the craft textile manufactures typical of the Campania region in Italy, and the heritage frame of the ancient textile techniques.

By connecting knowledge – such as contemporary art, textile manipulation, advanced manufacturing processes – the work will investigate an experimental circular fashion system through the hybridization of particular artisanal techniques and software, in order to develop new creative industries, with the aim of spreading a trans-disciplinary and digital fashion culture among stakeholders as well as citizens.

FOLLOW OUR PROGRESS

4. LET'S PUT ON A SHOW!

Following such intense research, work and creation, the only logical next step would be to show the world what we've done. What better way to promote sustainable fashion, than to put on a show.

Each partner city will host a fashion show, with video mapping installations and the results of the works on display. The events themselves will take place in 2 separate days: one with the fashion exhibition & artistic show (performing arts, urban dancing, video projections, light and sound structures, etc.) and the other one with a series of round-tables and debates to discuss relevant topics and engage the audience to participate in the process.

FOLLOW OUR PROGRESS

- vi. Partners: This page is dedicated to informing the public of the partner's university/organization, its research methodology and their role in the Fashion Alive project.

<https://fashion-alive.com/partners>

MEET THE PARTNERS

WE'RE A CREATIVE
EUROPE FUNDED
COLLABORATION

Fashion Alive is a Creative Europe funded project, consisting of partners from four European countries (Spain, Portugal, Italy, Austria). We will be collaborating to promote sustainable practices in the creative fashion industry via attractive events that engage wider audiences, raise awareness and ignite a discussion on the topic.

EXPERIMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

Our partners will conceptualize and experiment with the creation of sustainable fashion methods. Each partner will be working on the topic through a specific approach and methodology, with the results of their work being displayed via 3 non-conventional fashion and arts events that will combine the exhibition/catwalk of the sustainable creations with digital and audio-visual creations, as well as other added artistic actions.

The events will take place during 2 different days, as there will be another more participative session with round tables, talks, conferences and public discussions about arts, sustainability, fashion and creativity. We will be providing access to project developments and results thanks to our online dissemination activities as well as relaying our experiences each step of the way.

CREAMODITE

CREAMODITE is a Spanish association of ateliers of arts and design, with the main mission of activating and recovering the value of the local creative industries, most notably fashion.

CREAMODITE offers artistic experiences through unique events, fashion shows and workshops, in which the public and consumers are encouraged to actively participate. Relying on the support of relevant personalities in the world of fashion, including designers, dressmakers, patternmakers, visual and plastic artists, photographers and architects, CREAMODITE also collaborates regularly with fashion institutes, universities, business centers and local trade associations.

Through FASHION ALIVE, the association would like to go further and engage with international partners to provide a holistic combination of sustainable methods together with avant-garde cultural expressions. CREAMODITE brings their expertise in the Zero Waste Fashion field and combines their knowledge of artistic direction and event management (as well as choreography) in performances and conceptualisation.

THE CREAMODITE METHODOLOGY WILL EXPLORE THE ZERO WASTE FASHION CONCEPT BY DEVELOPING A PATTERNMAKING TECHNIQUE THAT AIMS AT REDUCING THE GARMENTS WASTE TOWARDS ZERO BY GENERATING PATTERN SILHOUETTES THAT ARE NOT PRE-DEFINED BY THE BODY SHAPE, THUS EASING THE CUTTING AND DRESSMAKING PROCESSES.

FOLLOW THEIR PROGRESS

UMINHO

The Department of Textile Engineering at the School of Engineering at the CENTRO DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA TÊXTEIL DA UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO in Guimarães (Portugal) has been developing research activities in the area of Fibrous Material Engineering and Design for a few decades now. Their main objective has been to enhance the competitive position of the European Industries by building a knowledge base on science and technology of fibrous materials and processes.

At FASHION ALIVE, UMINHO will focus on the surface design from post-consumer clothing disposal and their use in experimental clothing design. Following these principles, a series of experimental designs will be carried out throughout the project, which will also combine some elements extracted from CREAMCOTTE and UCAMPANIA techniques.

The UMINHO methodology will explore the creation of fashion elements by using recycled materials coming from second-hand clothes or other sustainable materials. UMINHO techniques will then stem from the concept of Circular Fashion to promote the use of materials that can represent a significant environmental waste reduction for the environment.

UMINHO IS CURRENTLY WORKING ON CIRCULAR FASHION, FOCUSING ON SURFACE DESIGN FROM POST-CONSUMER CLOTHING DISPOSAL AND THEIR USE IN EXPERIMENTAL CLOTHING DESIGN.

FOLLOW THEIR PROGRESS

UNICAMPANIA

The Department of Architecture and Industrial Design at the University of Campania carries out, promotes and supports research, basic and applied, in the fields of architecture, industrial design, cultural heritage, urban context, of the government of the territory and of the landscape. UCAMPANIA possesses a Slow Fashion Thinking considering the fashion industry as a model of social and cultural responsibility, for the manufacture of products based on the promotion of cultural values and a sustainable local supply chain.

In the FASHION ALIVE Project, UCAMPANIA will focus its research on the field of environmental sustainability of the fashion industry in Campania by analysing handmade manufactures: footwear, men's tailoring, eco-sustainable leather processing.

In the context of the project, UCAMPANIA will apply an innovative use of advanced digital technologies within the heritage frame of the ancient textile techniques typical from the Campania region.

Moving around a transdisciplinary vision that connects different knowledge – such as contemporary art, textile manipulation, advanced manufacturing processes – the work will investigate an experimental circular fashion system through the hybridization of particular artisanal techniques and software, in order to develop new creative industries. UCAMPANIA will as well create their unique exhibition event at Caserta and organise the pertinent roundtables to discuss hot topics on sustainability, cultural heritage and fashion.

UNICAMPANIA IS CURRENTLY WORKING ON THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE HERITAGE THROUGH THE HYBRIDIZATION OF PARTICULAR ARTISANAL TECHNIQUES OF THE CAMPANIA REGION AND SOFTWARE, IN ORDER TO DEVELOP NEW CREATIVE INDUSTRIES.

FOLLOW THEIR PROGRESS

XSENTRIK ARTS

Xsentrik Arts is an Austrian non-profit arts organization that acts as an interdisciplinary arts platform with a focus on utilizing the power of storytelling to inspire and create change, promote diversity and equality, advocate sustainable, healthy living solutions and dialogue in lives and spaces.

XSENTRIK projects focus on utilizing the power of storytelling to inspire and create change; to promote diversity equally; to advocate sustainable, healthy living solutions and dialogue in lives and spaces; and to activate or promote stories, places, people who are engaged in projects that activate or regenerate buildings, communities, and societies. Members of the association come from numerous backgrounds, including culture, applied arts, filmmaking, contemporary architecture and urbanism, computer programming, social work and community outreach. As a result, their work is diverse, and unabashedly combines knowledge and know-how from various fields.

Over the years, XSENTRIK created exposés on urban space and community based living, documentaries on sustainability and cultural preservation, films on social inclusion and equal opportunity, as well as community projects promoting civic activation and regeneration through community involvement.

XSENTRIKARTS will explore and envisage a digital and audio-visual strategy using technological tools (combining videos, 3-D projections, video mapping software, sounds, lights and music created by artificial intelligence, temporary architecture, etc.) that will be adapted to a live fashion show, showcasing the zero waste fashion concepts developed by our partners.

XSENTRIK ARTS IS CURRENTLY WORKING ON COMMUNICATIONS FOR THE FASHION ALIVE PROJECT, AS WELL AS DESIGNING AND PRODUCING VIDEOMAPPING INSTALLATIONS FOR THE FASHION SHOWS.

FOLLOW THEIR PROGRESS

- vii. Contact: A contact form has been created so that website visitors can contact the project organisation, regarding the project, its partners, or any other inquiries.

<https://fashion-alive.com/contact-us>

FASHION ALIVE Home News About Contact Partners

CONTACT US

Simply drop us a line, and we promise to get back to you!

NAME

EMAIL

MESSAGE

2. Social Media Channels

The project will be utilising two main social media outlets: Facebook and Instagram.

While Facebook will provide posting of content, links, and updates, Instagram will help bring the visual aspect of the project and the designs to the spotlight. Both platforms will assist in reaching target audience groups.

https://www.instagram.com/fashion_alive_22/

<https://www.facebook.com/fashionalive22>

a. Social Media post formats:

Social media is a space in which various formats and content types can be shared. In this regard, we will keep the formats and styles fluid. For instance, posting during the Fashion Events will require the use of Instagram and more immediate aesthetics, while posting videos will require a different approach.

In general however, most news items will be posted via a uniform design template, which can be accompanied with other photos and additional materials.

The following graphic design template can be adapted, and the images used can be changed to fit the message being disseminated.

When the message is text based, the text format can be used to focus on the message and meaning.

formats.

Images of the social media post

b. Social media activity:

To date, 8 posts have been created and shared on Instagram, and 7 on Facebook.

Instagram posts:

fashion_alive_22 ...

fashion_alive_22 Are you a pattern maker, designer, or a self-taught creator of fashion? Do you also believe fashion needs to be sustainable, with least impact on our planet, environment, society and future? Then this contest is for you! Submit your designs before 11/20/2022 to win a spot on the Fashion Alive Madrid 2023 catwalk. More information at the following link on our website: <https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-launches-contests-2>

Ver estadísticas

45 reproducciones

OCTUBRE 21

Agrega un comentario... Publicar

fashion_alive_22 ...

fashion_alive_22 Zero Waste Fashion is a technique that creates garments with the least amount of waste possible, encouraging a more environmentally friendly fashion industry. Our Spanish partner @creamodite @creamodite visited a bag manufacturer (ladybolsos.es) recently, to discuss possibilities for manufacturing zero-waste bags. The meeting went great, and exchanged ideas on how leather is more sustainable as a biodegradable, long-lasting option. Read more on our website: <https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-launches-contests-2>

Ver estadísticas

Les gusta a creamodite y 20 personas más

OCTUBRE 29

Agrega un comentario... Publicar

fashion_alive_22 ...

fashion_alive_22 What is the Fashion Alive project? We're an international collaboration promoting sustainable fashion practices. We aim to raise public awareness through fashion events and discussions. So follow us and remain in the loop, because we have some amazing fashion shows with #circular and #zerowaste designs, with video mapping and performances coming up in #madrid, #italy and #portugal! #fashion #zerowastefashion #sustainablefashion

Ver estadísticas

Les gusta a creamodite y 25 personas más

NOVIEMBRE 18

Agrega un comentario... Publicar

Facebook posts:

Fashion Alive
16 de noviembre a las 10:40

What is the Fashion Alive project?
We're an international collaboration promoting sustainable fashion practices.
We aim to raise public awareness through fashion events and discussions. So follow us and remain in the loop, because we have some amazing fashion shows with #fashionalive and #zerowaste designs, with video mapping and performances coming up in #madrid, #italy and #portugal!
#fashion #zerowastefashion #sustainablefashion
www.fashion-alive.com

THE FUTURE OF SUSTAINABLE FASHION

RAISING AWARENESS AND IGNITING DEBATE ON SUSTAINABLE FASHION DESIGN.

FOLLOW OUR PROGRESS
FASHION-ALIVE.COM

FASHION ALIVE Funded by the European Union

Fashion Alive
25 de octubre

Zero Waste Fashion is a technique that creates garments with the least amount of waste possible, encouraging a more environmentally friendly fashion industry.
Our Spanish partner @Creamodite @creamodite visited a bag manufacturer (ladybolsos.es) recently, to discuss possibilities for manufacturing zero-waste bags. The meeting went great, and exchanged ideas on how leather is more sustainable as a biodegradable, long-lasting option. Read more on our website: <https://fashion-...> Ver más

Fashion Alive
21 de octubre

Are you a pattern maker, designer, or a self-taught creator of fashion?
Do you also believe fashion needs to be sustainable, with least impact on our planet, environment, society and future?
Then this contest is for you!
Submit your designs before 11/20/2022 to win a spot on the Fashion Alive Madrid 2023 catwalk. More information on the competition(s) and how to apply: <https://fashion-alive.com/fashion-alive-launches-contests-2...> Ver más

SELECTED DESIGNS INCLUDED AS PART OF THE FASHION ALIVE RUNWAY SHOW

19.05.2023
EL ATENEO, MADRID

HOW TO PARTICIPATE >>>>>>

Fashion Alive
19 de octubre

Our project partners @Creamodite and Xentrik Arts met in Madrid last week and visited the event venue: *Ateneo de Madrid* to take measurements for an ambitious projection mapping concept to accompany the catwalk, and discuss the planning of the Fashion Alive show. We will be promoting sustainable fashion through zero waste pattern-making and creative design, a fashion show and exchange, so stay tuned!

Fashion Alive
6 de octubre

It might not seem like it.... But this is a bag. A unique one, designed to be #zerowaste. By developing unique #geometric shapes in the #designs, we can ensure no material is discarded, or thrown to waste. Fashion Alive is a international project (funded by Creative Europe) aiming to promote #sustainable, #positive #fashion. Follow us, we've got lots coming your way!

zero waste FASHION

minimizes waste THROUGH creative DESIGN

3. Monitoring

At the time of the creation of this document, the KPI numbers for the website and social media were as follows:

Current numbers

Channel / Activity	Measurement Unit	Numbers
Instagram	Followers	237
Facebook	Page Likes	972
Website	Traffic Info.	N/A

We will be monitoring our social media outreach as our partners involve their networks and students; we will also be cross posting to relevant sites in order to increase our following and interaction rates.